

JOURNAL SECTION OR CONFERENCE SECTION

Partially resolved binary stars in Gaia

D.A. Chulkov^{1,*}¹*Institute of Astronomy of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 119017, Pyatnitskaya str., 48, Moscow, Russia*
(Received xx.xx.2025; Revised xx.xx.2025; Accepted xx.xx.2025)

Nowadays Gaia DR3 is one of the most widely used data products in astronomy. The difference in pipelines for *G*, *BP* and *RP* photometry induces artifacts specific to double stars with $0.1 \lesssim \rho \lesssim 2$ arcsec angular separation, which can be easily misinterpreted and are addressed in this manuscript.

PACS numbers: 95.80.+p

Keywords: binary stars – Gaia – photometry

1. INTRODUCTION

Gaia is a space observatory, launched in 2013 and actively operated by the European Space Agency until the beginning of 2025[1]. At the time of writing, Gaia Data Release 3[2] is one of the most actively used data products in astronomy. Below I address a few concepts related to binary and multiple stars observed by Gaia. For a broader perspective on multiplicity in Gaia data, I refer to the review[3] which summarizes the progress and sets expectations for the Data Release 4, scheduled for December 2026. The core part of Gaia DR3 is the main source catalog which contains 1.81 billion sources with the photometric data provided for most of them. The processing pipelines are different for *G* ($\lambda_0 = 673$, $\Delta\lambda = 440$ nm), *BP* ($\lambda_0 = 532$, $\Delta\lambda = 253$ nm) and *RP* ($\lambda_0 = 797$, $\Delta\lambda = 296$ nm) passbands[4] which may have an unexpected implication on data interpretation for some resolved binary stars.

Below, the Gaia acquisition procedure for *G* (Section 2), *BP* and *RP* (Section 3) photometric passbands is briefly outlined. In Section 4 some examples of the behavior of different binaries in Gaia data are given. The dependence of Gaia multipeak fraction metrics on angular separation is explored in Section 5. A short summary in Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. BINARY STARS IN THE G PASSBAND

Gaia continuously scanned the celestial sphere (34 months of observations passed to the DR3 release), and the *G*-band photometry is an outcome of the image parameter determination procedure which involves point or line spread function analysis coming from its astrometric field instrument. It is calibrated on point-like sources, creating a bias for extended objects such as galaxies or binary stars. With the asymmetric primary mirrors, the angular resolution depends on scan direction. The sampling resolution of 0.059 arcsec per pixel is achieved in the along-scan orientation

and 0.177 arcsec per pixel in the orthogonal direction. The distribution of scan orientation angles is highly anisotropic for sources with ecliptic latitude $|\beta| < 45^\circ$. Thus, passages directed toward either east or west in ecliptic coordinates are completely avoided[5].

The percentage of scans when the secondary peak possibly associated with a companion is detected during image parameter determination routine is recorded in the *ipd_frac_multi_peak* metrics contained in the main source Gaia DR3 catalog. As part of the pipeline, the affected pixels are removed during the point spread function fitting to reduce the bias from the secondary source. Yet, a separate analysis of the secondary peaks is not provided in Gaia DR3, and only primary sources become part of the catalog. However, if Gaia fails to resolve a source, combined flux from both components contributes to the image parameter determination procedure. As a result, the provided *G* magnitude refers either to a brighter star alone after attempted subtraction of the secondary star contribution or to the whole system. A complex angle-dependent nature of Gaia survey means that the contamination level due to the secondary component depends on scanning direction and orientation of the binary star, thus creating an ambiguity for systems within the $0.1 \lesssim \rho \lesssim 0.3$ arcsec angular separation range[6]. A more advanced analysis aiming to recover binarity parameters is expected to be published as part of Gaia DR4 catalog.

3. BINARIES IN THE BP AND RP BANDS

A separate photometric instrument acquired data on *BP* and *RP* photometry. It measures spectral energy distribution within a rectangular 3.5×2.1 arcsec window, centered on the target source[7]. *BP* and *RP* magnitudes are the outcome of aperture photometry for the integrated spectra. Due to the large field, *BP* and *RP* data are prone to crowding effects and for double stars with $\rho \lesssim 1$ arcsec fluxes are combined from both components regardless of scan direction. This blending artifact makes systems in the $0.1 \lesssim \rho \lesssim 2$ arcsec separation range visible in Gaia color-color diagrams (Figure 1) as outliers. Moreover, based on open

* E-mail: chulkovd@gmail.com

cluster data discussed later, in case of large magnitude contrast, BP and RP fluxes for fainter stars can be contaminated at least up to $\rho \sim 10$ arcsec.

4. EXAMPLES

For instructive examples, Pleiades stars will be used. Gaia survey has brought a major development to the study of open clusters[9]. They represent a convenient test ground for catalog data validation being a coeval population. Member stars share the common origin and have nearly identical age while remaining a fairly compact group in space. As a result, they form a distinct sequence in the color-magnitude diagram (Figure 1). The offset in position can be a sign of stellar multiplicity or other peculiarity, such as excessive extinction, or wrong membership classification.

HD 23479 is a resolved binary star with angular separation between components $\rho = 1.06$ arcsec, and Gaia DR3 has separate entries for them (Table 1). Magnitude difference is $\Delta G \sim 1.2^{\text{mag}}$ in the G band. However, both BP and RP magnitudes show, surprisingly, that components have a similar brightness. The reported values correspond to combined flux from the system rather than individual components, which is the result of aperture photometry over the large field. The positions of both sources in the color-magnitude diagram (Figure 1) are compromised. Since HD 23479 is a Pleiades member, reliable empirical mass-magnitude relations exist for various passbands[10], and it is possible to derive BP and RP photometry based on G magnitudes alone. Combined magnitude for two stars with known mag_1 and mag_2 is calculated as $mag = -2.5 \log(10^{-mag_1/2.5} + 10^{-mag_2/2.5})$. For HD 23479, the derived BP and RP values are within 0.03^{mag} of those reported in Gaia DR3 (Table 1).

Table 1. Binary star HD 23479 with $\rho = 1.06''$ in Gaia DR3 (Section 4). Total BP and RP magnitudes are calculated based on G photometry and empirical isochrone from [10]. Adopted distance modulus 5.65^{mag} corresponds to 135 pc.

Band	Star 1	Star 2
Gaia DR3	65230764996027776	65230764998207232
G	$8.229 \pm 0.003^{\text{mag}}$	$9.409 \pm 0.004^{\text{mag}}$
BP	$8.105 \pm 0.008^{\text{mag}}$	$8.082 \pm 0.003^{\text{mag}}$
RP	$7.661 \pm 0.006^{\text{mag}}$	$7.678 \pm 0.015^{\text{mag}}$
Empirical isochrone estimate		
Mass	$1.67M_{\odot}$	$1.30M_{\odot}$
Total BP	8.07^{mag}	
Total RP	7.63^{mag}	

Another highlighted example is FL Tau. In this case only the Gaia DR3 65010175477867776 entry appears in the 12 arcsec radius. However, both the position in the color-color diagram (Figure 1) and a 80% value of $ipd_frac_multi_peak$ immediately signal binarity. Indeed, it was speckle-resolved with separation $\rho = 0.63$ arcsec and estimated mass ratio $q = 0.93$ [11]. The offset in the color-color diagram can be interpreted as

BP and RP excess over G flux. As in the previous example, G magnitude here corresponds to one star, while BP and RP come from the system as a whole.

The interpretation of BP and RP fluxes as a simple sum of individual fluxes is likely incorrect for systems wider than 1 arcsec, since the second component misses the photometer's window during some scans, although this regime was not carefully studied by the author. In such cases, BP and RP magnitudes are often omitted in Gaia DR3 for the fainter component, even if G magnitude is available. In the presence of a bright star, contamination of BP and RP magnitudes can occur at large separations. For example, Gaia DR3 66798526845337344 ($G = 13.8^{\text{mag}}$) which is a confident Pleiades member based on its astrometric solution, has contaminated BP and RP magnitudes by a star 21 Tau ($G = 5.8^{\text{mag}}$) located at $\rho \sim 9$ arcsec.

5. MULTYPEAK FRACTION

As shown in Figure 2, binaries with $0.1 \lesssim \rho \lesssim 2$ arcsec show $ipd_frac_multi_peak$ excess, unless the secondary flux is too low, which makes this parameter a convenient predictor of subarcsecond multiplicity. The systems beyond this range generally show zero multipeak fraction. The exceptions are usually related to the presence of a third light. Angular separations in Figure 2 come from speckle measurements which occurred at a different epoch than Gaia DR3, so an orbital motion could slightly blur the distinction between zero and nonzero $ipd_frac_multi_peak$ cases.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Depending on angular separation (ρ) and other factors (component magnitudes, position angle, ecliptic latitude) binary systems behave photometrically in different regimes. The suggested classification should be treated with great caution as initial guidance only:

- Resolved in G , BP and RP , $\rho \gtrsim 2$ arcsec.
- Resolved in G , while BP and RP are partially contaminated, $1 \lesssim \rho \lesssim 2$ arcsec.
- Resolved in G , while BP and RP are unresolved, $0.3 \lesssim \rho \lesssim 1$ arcsec.
- Partially contaminated in G , while BP and RP are unresolved, $0.1 \lesssim \rho \lesssim 0.3$ arcsec.
- Unresolved in G , BP and RP , $\rho \lesssim 0.1$ arcsec.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This manuscript is largely inspired by the ongoing resolved multiplicity survey conducted at the Caucasian Observatory of Sternberg Astronomical Institute of Lomonosov Moscow State University.

FUNDING

The study was conducted under the state assignment of the Institute of Astronomy of the Russian Academy of Sciences.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author of this work declares that he has no conflicts of interest.

-
- [1] Gaia Collaboration, T. Prusti, J. de Bruijne, A. Brown, A. Vallenari, et al., *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 595, A1 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201629272>
- [2] Gaia Collaboration, A. Brown, A. Vallenari, T. Prusti, J. de Bruijne, et al., *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 649, A1 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202039657>
- [3] K. El-Badry, *New Astronomy Reviews*, 98, 101694 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.newar.2024.101694>
- [4] C. Jordi, M. Gebran, J. M. Carrasco, J. de Bruijne, et al. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 523, A48 (2010). <https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201015441>
- [5] B. Holl, C. Fabricius, J. Portell, L. Lindegren, et al. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 674, A25 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202245353>
- [6] K. Sullivan, A. Kraus, T. Berger, D. Huber, *The Astronomical Journal*, 169, 29 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/ad9330>
- [7] M. Riello, F. De Angeli, D.W. Evans, P. Montegriffo, et al., *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 649, A3 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202039587>
- [8] D. Chulkov, *The Astronomical Journal*, 168, 156 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/ad7025>
- [9] T. Cantat-Gaudin, L. Casamiquela, *New Astronomy Reviews*, 99, 101696 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.newar.2024.101696>
- [10] R. Liu, Z. Shao, Li, L., *The Astronomical Journal*, 169, 116 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/ada380>
- [11] D. Chulkov, I. Strakhov, B. Safonov, *The Astronomical Journal*, 169, 145 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/ada564>
- [12] A. Tokovinin and C. Briceño, *The Astronomical Journal*, 159, 15 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/ab5525>

Figure 1. Pleiades stars in the color-magnitude (left panel) and color-color diagrams (center and right panels) based on Gaia photometric passbands. Binary stars taken as examples in Section 4 are additionally marked. Note that both components of HD 23479 are present in Gaia DR3, while a sole entry exists for FL Tau. Based on data from [8].

Figure 2. The value of *ipd_frac_multi_peak* (multiplex fraction) in Gaia DR3 depending on angular separation for resolved multiple stars in Pleiades cluster (left) and Upper Scorpius association (right). The estimated mass ratio $q = m_2/m_1$ is shown with a color bar. Resolved triple stars are marked with triangles. Based on data from [11] and [12].